

A new Method of Preparing Organo-mercury Compounds of Phenols, Phenol-ethers and aromatic Amines.

P. NEOGI AND MANAS PRASUN CHATTERJI.

The preparation of aromatic compounds of mercury was first extensively undertaken by Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2154 *et seq.*) Pesci (*Gazzetta*, 1898, **28**, ii, 436 *et seq.*) and several others. The introduction of mercury into various organic compounds has hitherto almost uniformly been effected by heating them with mercuric acetate. In the case of mercuri-chlorides of aromatic organic compounds the acetate is decomposed by means of sodium chloride. Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 758) has shown that besides the acetate such mercuric salts as the sulphate and the nitrate, which are hydrolysed by water, are capable of acting on aromatic organic compounds: but mercuric chloride has been found to have very little action, if any, on aromatic compounds.

In this paper it has been shown that mercury derivatives of aromatic compounds can be prepared mostly in the cold by the action of mercuric chloride along with sodium bicarbonate on these compounds. Neogi and Neogi (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **131**, 30) have recently shown that a distinct period of induction exists when mercuric chloride and sodium bicarbonate are allowed to act before oxychlorides of mercury are precipitated. They have further shown that, amongst other substances, glycerol has the property of very largely increasing the period of induction in the interaction of mercuric chloride and sodium bicarbonate. Advantage has been taken of this phenomenon in this paper to prepare organic mercury compounds of aromatic phenols, phenol-ethers and amines by adding the organic compound to the mixture of sodium bicarbonate and mercuric chloride in the presence of glycerol. This is a very interesting phenomenon, as it shows the possibility of formation of compounds with new reactants added during the period of induction before the main reaction finds time to be completed. As the formation of oxychloride of mercury requires time which might be indefinitely increased by the presence of glycerol, the organic compounds introduced in the mixture combine with the reactants and form new

compounds. The organic substance and mercuric chloride solution are mixed together, glycerol is then added followed by the sodium bicarbonate solution. Sometime the order of the addition is reversed. In the case of substances not soluble in water alcoholic solutions are taken. This method might be made a general process of preparing organo-mercury compounds.

The reactions that take place in the case of phenols and phenol-ethers may be represented by the following equations:

In the case of catechol, quinol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, guaiacol and orcinol, mono- and di-oxydimercuri-chlorides of the phenols and phenol-ethers are formed as the case may be. In the case of phenol however *o*- and *p*-hydroxyphenylene mercuri-chlorides are formed according to the equation:—

So far as amines are concerned it is to be remembered that mercuric chloride gives crystalline additive derivatives of the type $(C_6H_5NH_2)_2HgCl_2$ (Forster, *Annalen*, 1875, 175, 30). In order to prepare mercury derivatives by this method, sodium bicarbonate solution was added first to aqueous or alcoholic solutions of the amines, and then the mercuric chloride solution was added. In the case of the amines the addition of glycerol is not necessary owing to the prior formation of the additive derivatives. In the case of primary and secondary aromatic amines the following equations represent the reactions that take place:—

In the case of tertiary amines the $HgCl$ radical replaces a hydrogen in the benzene nucleus or forms a complex molecule,

As regards the question whether the radical HgCl enters the nucleus or forms oxy-mercurichlorides in the case of phenols and phenol-ethers the following experimental evidences point to the formation of oxy mercuri-chlorides excepting in the case of phenol:—

1. These mercury compounds except that of phenol are not soluble in caustic soda and hence do not contain phenolic hydroxyl groups.

2. These compounds are generally decomposed by caustic soda into mercuric chloride and the sodium derivatives of original phenols.

3. These oxy-mercuri-chlorides are new compounds which do not correspond in properties to mercuri-chloride derivatives of phenols in which the radical HgCl has entered the nucleus.

In the case of the amino-compounds the HgCl radical replaces the hydrogen in the amino-group and not in the nucleus as the usual evidences of the presence of amino-groups, such as the formation of azo-dyes in the case of primary amines, are wanting in the case of these compounds. As regards tertiary amines, owing to the absence of hydrogen in the amino-group, the HgCl radical replaces hydrogen in the nucleus.

These oxy-mercuri-chlorides are generally white or light yellow in colour. The catechol compound is green and the guaiacol compound is deep yellow. The amino-compounds are generally yellow in colour. They are all insoluble in water and in most organic solvents. They are mostly soluble in hot mineral acids but insoluble in caustic soda which decomposes them. The mercury compounds prepared by this new method from catechol, oreinol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, guaiacol, and quinol are new compounds. The yield is quite good.

As regards analytical results the mercury was estimated by two methods: (1) Marsh and Lye's method (*Analyst*, 1917, **42**, 84), and (2) Francois' method (*Compt. rend.*, 1918, **166**, 950, and *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1920, [IV], **27**, 568). As regards the former method our experience is that it is best to increase the proportion of calcium sulphate to four or five times instead of twice the weight of the substance to be analysed in order to prevent the distillation of tarry matter. Even with this precaution the free mercury obtained, specially in the case of amino-compounds, was found to be contaminated with small quantities of brown organic matter. In those cases therefore the mercury was washed with ether before drying and weighing. As regards Francois' method our experience is that it gives good results though it takes nearly four days to get the final weight of the mercury. The advantage of Francois' method however lies in the

fact that several estimations can be started in one day and the result obtained simultaneously at the end of four days. Both these methods of estimating mercury in organic compounds are to be recommended in preference to the usual method of estimating it as HgS after the destruction of organic matter in a sealed tube in a Carius' furnace.

The chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method which works well in the case of these compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o and *p*-Hydroxyphenylene mercurichloride, $C_6H_4 \begin{cases} (OH)(1) \\ HgCl(2),(4) \end{cases}$

Phenol (10 g.) was dissolved in water and glycerol (10 c c) was added and an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (6 g) was next poured in. No precipitate was obtained, but on addition of sodium bicarbonate solution and stirring, a yellowish white precipitate was obtained. On the addition of a small quantity of very dilute hydrochloric acid or a strong solution of sodium chloride the colour changed to white. The same compound was prepared by converting the phenol to sodium phenate by the addition of the requisite quantity of caustic soda and then adding mercuric chloride and sodium bicarbonate. The addition of glycerol in the case of sodium phenate is not necessary. The white precipitate obtained in either case was filtered and thoroughly washed with water. It was found to be partially soluble in alcohol and also in hot water. It was therefore first exhausted with boiling alcohol in an invert condenser and the alcoholic solution filtered through a hot filter. On cooling a white crystalline precipitate was obtained. This was recrystallised from hot alcohol, dried, analysed and tested and were found to be *p* hydroxyphenylene mercuric chloride prepared by Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2154).

The substance dissolves in caustic soda without decomposition and melts at about 219°.

The residue after extraction with alcohol was then dissolved in hot water and filtered through a hot filter. The solution on cooling deposited white crystals which were found to be *o* hydroxyphenylene mercuric chloride (m p 133°), $(OH) C_6H_4 \cdot HgCl(2)$ prepared by Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2154) (Found Hg, 60.01; Cl, 9.98. C_6H_4OHgCl requires Hg, 60.94, Cl, 10.77 per cent.)

o-Phenylenedioxy-dimercuri-chloride, $C_6H_4(OHgCl)_2$,

Catechol (4 g.) was dissolved in an excess of water and glycerol (10 c.c.) was added and then an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (16 g.) was poured in. A solution of sodium bicarbonate (5 g.) was then gradually added when effervescence occurred and a green precipitate was formed. It was then filtered off and thoroughly washed with water and dried.

It was found to be insoluble in alcohol, chloroform and other organic solvents. It was very readily decomposed by caustic soda and ammonia and was insoluble in dilute mineral acids. It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid giving a green solution and decomposed at 150° to a black powder.

Judged by the above properties and analysis the substance appears to be *o*-phenylene dioxy-di-mercurichloride. (Found: Hg, 68.20; Cl, 13.74. $C_6H_4O_2Hg_2Cl_2$ requires Hg, 69.15; Cl, 12.22 per cent.).

It is to be noted that catechol has not yet been mercurated. Dimroth reported (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 758) that catechol did not form any mercury derivatives but only reduced their mercuric acetate. The preparation of oxy-mercuri-chloride of catechol by this method is therefore a distinct step in the preparation of mercury compounds of catechol.

m-Phenylenedioxy-dimercurichloride.

Resorcinol (5 g.) was dissolved in excess of water and then on the addition of glycerol (15 c. c.), mercuric chloride (20 g.) and finally sodium bicarbonate solution (6 g.), a voluminous white precipitate was produced. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, thoroughly washed with water and dried. The substance was found to be insoluble in alcohol, acetone, ether, chloroform and other organic solvents. It was also insoluble in caustic soda which readily decomposed it. The substance decomposed at 210° without melting.

Analysis and the properties of the compound would make it to be *m*-phenylene dioxy-dimercuri-chloride. (Found: Hg, 69.30; Cl, 11.60. $C_6H_4O_2Hg_2Cl_2$ requires Hg, 69.15; Cl, 12.22 per cent.)

It is to be noted that Dimroth and Metzger (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2853) prepared by the mercuric acetate method a mercuri-chloride derivative of resorcinol having the formula $C_6H_3(OH)_2.HgCl$ in which the $HgCl$ radical entered the nucleus which had properties different from the oxymercuri-chloride prepared by us. Dimroth's compound is soluble in chloroform and melts at 123° whilst our compound is insoluble in chloroform and decomposes at 210° without melting. The above authors have also prepared a di-mercuri-chloride derivative (*loc. cit.*) of resorcinol $C_6H_3(OH)_2.(HgCl)_2$ which decomposes at 200° without melting and is soluble in ether whilst our compound is insoluble in ether.

Orcinol dioxy-dimercurichloride, $(1)CH_3.C_6H_3(OHgCl)_2(3:5)$ —Five gm. of orcinol (in excess of water), 20 gm. of mercuric chloride, 5 gm. of sodium bicarbonate and 5 c.c. of glycerol were taken. The mixture was left undisturbed for about an hour for allowing the precipitate to settle. It was then filtered and thoroughly washed with water. The substance was found to be insoluble in ordinary organic solvents. It dissolves completely in hot dilute nitric and hydrochloric acids and also in hot glacial acetic acid. It is decomposed by caustic soda. The substance decomposes completely at 210° without melting.

The substance would correspond to the formula for orcinol dioxy-di-mercurichloride as judged by its analysis and properties. (Found : Hg, 67.74 ; Cl, 12.22. $C_7H_6O_2.Hg_2Cl_2$ requires Hg, 67.51 ; Cl, 11.93 per cent.).

o-Methoxyphenyleneoxy-mercurichloride, $(1)CH_3O.C_6H_4.OHgCl(2)$.—Guaiacol (3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and then glycerol (20 c.c.) and a solution of sodium bicarbonate (2 g.) were added to it. An aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (6 g.) was next poured in. The deep yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with alcohol and then with water. The substance was found to be insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone and benzene. It is decomposed by caustic soda and ammonia solutions. It dissolves in excess of conc. hydrochloric acid and also in warm conc. nitric acid. It decomposes at 130° without melting. Analysis and the properties of the compound point out its constitution to be *o*-methoxy phenylene oxy-mercuri-chloride. (Found : Hg, 56.22; Cl, 8.95. $C_7H_7O_2.HgCl$ requires Hg, 55.85; Cl, 9.87 per cent.). Efsio Mameli (*Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, ii, 23) obtained guaiacol 4:6-dimercuri-dichloride as a white crystalline powder (by the mercuric acetate

and sodium chloride method) which decomposes at 179°-180° and is therefore different from our compound.

Phloroglucinol tri-oxy-tri-mercurichloride, C₆H₃(OHgCl)₃.

One gm. of phloroglucinol, 12 gm. of sodium bicarbonate, 6 gm. of mercuric chloride and 2 c.c. of glycerol were taken. In this case a white precipitate was formed which on filtration and washing assumed a light yellow colour. The substance is soluble in conc. hydrochloric acid with decomposition but insoluble in dil caustic soda. The powder decomposes at 160° without melting. (Found: Hg, 71.93; Cl, 12.41. C₆H₃O₃Hg₃Cl₃ requires Hg, 72.39; Cl, 12.79 per cent.).

No mercurichloride derivative of phloroglucinol is known, a mercuri-acetate compound only being obtained by Lyes (*J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1905, 6, 388). The oxy-mercuri chloride prepared here is therefore a new mercury compound of phloroglucinol.

p-Phenylene dioxy-di-mercurichloride, C₆H₄(OHgCl)₂.

As regards quinol, Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2853) has reported that it does not form a mercury compound with mercuric acetate but is simply oxidised to quinhydrone. Using our method we have been able to prepare an oxy-mercuri-chloride derivative of quinol but owing to its ready oxidisability quinol is partially oxidised to quinone (and hence to quinhydrone) which is recognised by its characteristic odour. The quinone partly reduces mercuric chloride to mercurous chloride and even to metallic mercury when the reaction is very vigorous. The resultant product is therefore not pure oxy-mercurichloride, and as it is not soluble in ordinary organic solvents it was not possible to purify it. Nevertheless this method is an improvement over Dimroth's in the fact that a distinct mercuri-chloride of quinol is actually formed though not in a pure condition.

Four gm. of quinol, 16 gm. mercuric chloride, 5 gm. of sodium bicarbonate and 10 c.c. of glycerol were taken. The quinol was dissolved in excess of water and on the addition of the other substances a white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was allowed to settle and then filtered and washed with alcohol and water.

The white precipitate obtained as above was found to be insoluble in alcohol, chloroform and other organic solvents. It is readily decomposed by caustic soda and ammonia. It is insoluble in dil.

mineral acids. It decomposes at about 160° without melting. The substance on analysis and as regards properties was found to contain *p*-phenylene di-oxydi-mercuri-chloride. (Found: Hg, 75.48; Cl, 15.16. $C_6H_4O_2HgCl_2$, requires Hg, 69.15; Cl, 12.22 per cent.).

That the substance is not pure *p*-phenylene di-oxy-dimercuri-chloride is judged by the fact that the mercury and chlorine are too high owing to the reduction of oxy-mercurichloride partly to mercurous chloride which cannot be avoided.

Amino-Compounds.

Most of the aromatic amines form white crystalline additive derivatives with mercuric chloride alone. It has been shown that if sodium bicarbonate be added beforehand yellow mercury derivatives of the primary, secondary as well as tertiary amines are produced. The addition of glycerol is not necessary. The constitution has already been dealt with (p. 222).

Phenylamine mercurichloride, $C_6H_5NH_2.HgCl_2$.

Aniline (3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and a solution of sodium bicarbonate (3 g.) was added to it. A hot aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (9 g.) was next poured in when a yellow precipitate was formed. This was filtered off, washed repeatedly with alcohol and then with water. The compound was found to be insoluble in alcohol, ether and chloroform. It dissolved in dil. mineral acids.

Analysis and properties prove the compound to be phenylamine mercurichloride prepared by Forster (*loc. cit.*) by boiling an alcoholic solution of $(C_6H_5NH_2)_2HgCl_2$. (Found: Hg, 61.13. $C_6H_5NH_2.HgCl_2$ requires Hg, 61.13 per cent).

Monomethylaniline mercuri-chloride, $C_6H_5.NCH_3.HgCl_2$.

Mono-methylaniline (1 g.) was dissolved in excess of alcohol and a freshly prepared sodium bicarbonate (1 g.) solution was added to it. Alcoholic mercuric chloride (3 g.) was next poured in and the mixture was well shaken. The yellow precipitate was then filtered and thoroughly washed with alcohol.

The substance is an amorphous yellow powder which on exposure to light turns greenish. It is insoluble in water and alcohol and begins to decompose at 108° .

Analysis and properties prove the compound to be monomethyl-aniline mercuri-chloride. (Found : Hg, 58·13. C_7H_8NHgCl requires Hg, 58·62 per cent.).

This substance is similar in composition and properties to the compound prepared by Pesci (*Gazzetta*, 1892, 22, ii, 32) by the action of hydrochloric acid on methyl-phenyl-mercuriammonium hydroxide.

p-Mercurodiphenylenetetramethylmercurodiammonium Chloride.

To a dilute alcoholic solution of dimethylaniline a freshly prepared aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate was gradually poured in, taking care that no separation of the dimethylaniline took place. An alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride was immediately introduced and the whole thoroughly shaken and then left for an hour or two. The yellow precipitate was then filtered and washed with alcohol. It was then dissolved in boiling alcohol from which on cooling shining colourless crystals were obtained.

The substance is soluble in boiling benzene, alcohol and xylene, and also in water. It begins to decompose at 195° to a bluish substance and at about 215° the colour changes to deep brown.

The substance was identical with *p*-mercurodiphenylenetetramethyl-mercurio-diammonium chloride prepared by Pesci (*Gazzetta*, 1894, 23, ii, 521) by the action of yellow mercuric oxide on dimethylaniline chloride. (Found : Hg, 56·84. $(C_6H_8NHgCl)_2$ requires Hg, 56·31 per cent.).

An almost identical compound was obtained by Michaelis and Rabinerson (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2342) by the action of mercuric chloride on mercurio-dimethylaniline and given the formula, $HgCl. C_6H_4.N(CH_3)_2$.

In conclusion we would like to point out that the organo-mercury-compounds prepared by this method might be multiplied to an indefinite extent and the process might therefore be made a general method of preparing aromatic mercury compounds.

